

1 **Historical changes in seasonal aerosol acidity in**
2 **the Po Valley (Italy) as inferred from fog water**
3 **and aerosol measurements**

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36 thermodynamics.

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38 **ABSTRACT**

39 Acidity profoundly affects almost every aspect that shapes the composition of ambient particles
40 and their environmental impact. Thermodynamic analysis of gas-particle composition datasets
41 offers robust estimates of acidity, but are not available for long periods of time. Fogs composition
42 datasets are available for many decades; we develop a thermodynamic analysis to estimate the
43 ammonia in equilibrium with fog water, and to infer the pre-fog aerosol pH starting from fog
44 chemical composition and pH. The acidity values from the new method agree with the results of
45 thermodynamic analysis of available gas-particle composition data. Applying the new method to
46 historical (25 year) fog water composition at the rural station of San Pietro Capofiume (SPC) in
47 the Po Valley (Italy) suggests that the aerosol has been mildly acidic, with its pH decreasing by
48 0.5-1.5 pH units over the last decades. Observed fog water pH also increased 1 unit over the same
49 period. Analysis of the simulated aerosol pH reveals that the aerosol acidity trend is driven by
50 decreases of aerosol precursor concentrations, and changes in temperature and relative humidity.
51 Currently, NO_x controls would be most effective for PM_{2.5} reduction in the Po valley both during
52 summer and winter. In the future however, seasonal transitions to the NH₃-sensitive region may
53 occur, meaning that NH₃ reduction policy may become increasingly necessary.

54

55 **1. Introduction**

56 Aerosol acidity is a key driver of many important atmospheric processes^{1,2}, affecting partitioning
57 of semivolatile species, SOA formation, and solubilization of trace metals, with important
58 implications for air quality, human and ecosystems health and climate. Despite its importance, the
59 direct measurement of the pH of atmospheric aerosol is highly challenging, with only few available

60 techniques for its determination^{3,4,5}. Indirect proxies (e.g., aerosol ionic molar ratios) have been
61 used extensively in the past to represent particle acidity, although their link with pH is largely
62 qualitative^{2,6,7}. The most reliable estimates of aerosol acidity to date are obtained through
63 thermodynamic analysis of ambient observations^{6,7,8}. In this approach, aerosol thermodynamic
64 models (such as ISORROPIA-II⁹) are applied to observations of concentrations of species in the
65 gas and aerosol phase that control the water uptake of the aerosol. If the observed gas-particle
66 partitioning of species sensitive to aerosol pH (e.g., $\text{NH}_3(\text{g})/\text{NH}_4^+$, $\text{HNO}_3(\text{g})/\text{NO}_3^-$) and liquid water
67 content (W) are sufficiently captured by the thermodynamic model, the pH calculated from the
68 thermodynamic model would be a good estimate of the true value⁵.

69 Using thermodynamic analysis, datasets of aerosol acidity are appearing with increasing
70 frequency (see the review by Pye et al.²), however their number and temporal span is limited
71 compared to the large number of PM composition datasets available, because the required
72 concurrent measurements of the gas-phase concentrations of NH_3 and/or HNO_3 is often
73 unavailable. In most cases, even if it may not be the case for dust or sea salt particles, NH_3
74 concentration is enough to derive aerosol acidity, as it acts as a buffer that controls aerosol pH^{1,10}.
75 In the absence of NH_3 data, one can still obtain robust pH estimates if $\text{NO}_3^-/\text{HNO}_3$ observations
76 are available¹¹. If neither HNO_3 or NH_3 observations are available, the pH estimates can still be
77 obtained, albeit with a constrained (but non-negligible) bias^{8,12}.

78 To date, thermodynamic analysis has been applied exclusively to aerosol–gas phase
79 composition data. This approach is the most straightforward, as it provides the direct input required
80 by thermodynamic models to calculate semi-volatile partitioning and aerosol pH. Other non-
81 conventional datasets, however, may provide aerosol pH with an appropriately formulated
82 thermodynamic analysis. Fog water data offer such a potential, as fogs – which act like natural

83 “mist chamber” samplers - tend to scavenge significant fractions of aerosol mass and soluble
84 vapors such as NH_3 , HNO_3 and HCl . Gilardoni et al.¹³ showed that aerosol down to about 100 nm
85 was scavenged by fog droplets in the Po Valley – so most of the mass that controls aerosol pH was
86 contained in the fog water. Fog water pH and liquid water content can also be directly measured,
87 allowing for estimations of gas-phase aerosol precursors (the main ones being NH_3 , HNO_3 and
88 HCl ¹⁴). Combining this fog water and gas-phase information allows for a thermodynamic analysis
89 that can be used to constrain the pre-fog aerosol acidity. A combined aerosol-fog water
90 thermodynamic analysis is also important to understand the role of aerosols in fogs as media for
91 production of secondary organic aerosol, especially during intense haze events¹⁵.

92 In this study, we evaluate the potential of using fog water ionic composition data to estimate
93 the pH of the preexisting aerosol. The method is evaluated using data collected in the Po Valley
94 of Italy. Concurrent measurements of aerosol and gas phase composition, before fog events are
95 also used to estimate aerosol pH and are compared against the fog water-derived values. The fog
96 water-based method is then applied to the full dataset, which covers a period of over 25 years¹².
97 The resulting aerosol pH trend is then compared against the fog water pH trend and its links to the
98 emissions of aerosol precursors (i.e., SO_2 , NO_x and NH_3) and meteorological parameters (T and
99 RH) are explored.

100

101

102 **2. Experimental methods**

103 *2.1. Fog water collection and analysis*

104 Fog water has been collected systematically at the field station of San Pietro Capofiume (SPC)
105 since 1989 from November to March. A series of intensive fog campaigns also took place in SPC

106 during the 1980's^{17,18,19,20}. Fog water is sampled using an automated active string collector
107 extensively described by Fuzzi et al.²¹. The collector consists of a system in which fog droplets,
108 carried by the air stream created by a fan located at the rear part of a short wind tunnel, are forced
109 to impact on a series of strings. The impacted droplets then coalesce with each other and drain off
110 the stainless-steel strings into a funnel to eventually be collected in a sampling bottle. The air flow
111 through the tunnel is approximately $17 \text{ m}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$ with a 50% collection efficiency of individual
112 string at approximately 3 mm droplet radius.

113 A Particulate Volume Monitor PVM-100, measures the liquid water content of the fog
114 (LWC_f) with a time resolution of 1 min. This monitor is used to activate the string collector when
115 LWC_f exceeds 0.08 g m^{-3} . This threshold corresponds to a visibility of approximately 200 m^{22} and
116 the fog is considered dense (the meteorological definition of fog is visibility less than 1 km).

117 Direct pH measurements are carried out in the liquid fog samples with a Crison micropH
118 2002 pH meter: this measure is taken in the laboratory of ISAC-CNR (at Bologna, about 40 Km
119 far from SPC) as soon as the sample arrive from the field. Usually it happens after a short trip by
120 car (30-40 min. of transport). If for any reasons the time is longer, the fog sample is kept
121 refrigerated in fridge or directly outside (closed in the corked sampling bottle, on the terrace of the
122 laboratory) for at least 60 minutes in order to rebalance the temperature as much as possible with
123 that of the ambient air. Fog water samples are filtered (47 mm quartz-fiber filters) within a few
124 hours after collection to remove any suspended particles. The samples are then stored frozen until
125 the chemical analysis. Liquid samples are analyzed for inorganic ions (NH_4^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} ,
126 Cl^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-}) and low molecular weight organic acids (acetate, formate, methanesulfonate and
127 oxalate) by ion chromatography²³. The results of this chemical characterization and the temporal
128 trends in the observed chemical and physical parameters have been presented by Giulianelli et

129 al.¹⁶. As reported in Giulianelli et al.¹⁶, analytical problems affected chromatographic data from
130 1989/90 to 1992/93 and these samples are excluded from our analysis. A total of 577 fog water
131 samples were analyzed from November 1993 to December 2018, with an annual median number
132 of samples of 23 (4-37). The smallest number of samples corresponds to the central years of the
133 time series (2004-2006), for which the statistics should be considered less robust.

134

135 *2.2. PM_{2.5} and ammonia measurements*

136 Daily PM_{2.5} and gaseous ammonia (NH₃) measurements were made by the Regional Agency for
137 prevention, environment and energy (ARPAE) of Emilia-Romagna, Italy. The PM_{2.5} filter
138 sampling started in the framework of the Supersito project (www.arpae.it/supersito) from
139 November 2011 and continues until today following the protocol described by Ricciardelli et al.²⁴.
140 PM_{2.5} daily samples are collected at SPC on quartz fiber filters (PALL Tissu Quartz 2500 QAO-
141 UP 2500 47 mm filters) for the analysis of the major inorganic ions (NH₄⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺,
142 Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻). After the collection with a Single Channel Monitor (SWAM FAI Rome, Italy)
143 operating at the standard flowrate of 38.3 L min⁻¹ (EN12341), the samples are extracted in 10 ml
144 of MilliQ water, sonicated for 15 min, filtered through 0.45 mm cellulose acetate filters and then
145 injected into an Ion Chromatography system (DIONEX, California, USA). Gaseous ammonia
146 (NH₃) hourly measurements are available at SPC starting from August 2017 thanks to a
147 chemiluminescence ammonia analyzer (Model 201E, Teledyne-API, San Diego CA, USA) of the
148 air quality network of ARPAE Emilia-Romagna (following a standard certified QA/QC procedure
149 ISO9001:2015, www.arpae.it, Section S1).

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151

152 *2.3. Meteorological data*

153 Daily maximum, minimum and mean values for T and RH are available at SPC since 1993.
154 Since 2007, hourly data are available by the Hydro-Meteo-Climate Service of ARPAE-ER
155 (simc.arpae.it/dext3r/). T and RH measurements are validated against data measured at SPC
156 continuously by a VAISALA meteorological station.

157

158 **3. Modeling methods**

159 *3.1. Thermodynamic analysis of fog water composition to obtain pre-fog aerosol pH*

160 The ISORROPIA-II (version 2.3) aerosol thermodynamic model⁶ (<http://isorro피아.epfl.ch>)
161 calculates the composition and phase state of a K⁺-Ca²⁺-Mg²⁺-NH₄⁺-Na⁺-SO₄²⁻-NO₃⁻-Cl⁻-water
162 inorganic aerosol in thermodynamic equilibrium with gas-phase precursors. ISORROPIA-II has
163 been extensively used to predict the liquid water content and pH for inorganic aerosol^{1,8,12,25,26,27}.
164 Similar to previous studies, the definition of pH used here is:

165
$$pH = -\log_{10} \gamma_{H^+} H_{aq}^+ = -\log_{10} \frac{1000 \gamma_{H^+} H_{air}^+}{W_i + W_o} \cong -\log_{10} \frac{1000 \gamma_{H^+} H_{air}^+}{W_i} \quad (1)$$

166 where γ_{H^+} is the hydronium ion activity coefficient (here assumed unity), H_{aq}^+ (mol L⁻¹) is the
167 hydronium ion concentration in the aerosol aqueous phase, H_{air}^+ (μg m⁻³) is the hydronium ion
168 concentration per volume of air, and W_i and W_o (μg m⁻³) are particle water concentrations
169 associated with the aerosol inorganic and organic species, respectively. The pH used here is
170 consistent with the pH_F definition of Pye et al.². In this work, we neglect the contribution of water
171 from organic species and their overall effect on water activity and pH. Guo et al.⁸, Song et al.⁷,
172 Vasilakos et al.²⁸, and Battaglia Jr. et al.²⁹ evaluated this assumption and found organics to have a
173 secondary effect on aerosol pH, somewhere between 0.15 and 0.3 pH units. So, since the organic

174 aerosol hygroscopicity is not measured in our study and given that neglecting W_o appears to have
175 only a minor impact on the pH characterization, we determine pH only considering W_i .

176 We used ISORROPIA-II in the partitioning (“forward”) mode for metastable aerosol. In
177 this configuration, the model calculates the equilibrium partitioning given the total concentration
178 (gas plus particles) of various species together with RH and T as input. Considering that fog
179 scavenging efficiency of inorganic species are generally larger than 70% and show little
180 variability^{13,30}, here we apply the partitioning mode using the ionic composition of fog water (as a
181 proxy of the particle composition and amount) and the corresponding gaseous ammonia
182 concentrations as estimated in Section 3.2.

183 The total (gas and aerosol) concentration of species i in the pre-fog atmosphere ($C_{i,air}$, μg
184 m^{-3}) is obtained by multiplying their concentration in fog water ($C_{i,fog}$, $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) with the liquid
185 water content of the fog (LWC_{air} , mL m^{-3}):

$$186 \quad C_{i,air} = C_{i,fog} \text{LWC}_f \quad (2)$$

187 Given the relatively high pH of the fog water some ammonia is in the gas phase. Its concentration
188 is estimated based on its measured fog water concentration and pH (section 3.2). This is added to
189 the concentration calculated using (2). A similar inference of gas-phase HNO_3 and HCl is deemed
190 unnecessary in this case, given the high value of pH and LWC_f of fogs in SPC²⁶.

191 We test in Section 4.1 the reliability of our approach on a limited subset of data for which
192 parallel measurements of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and $\text{NH}_3(\text{g})$ are available, comparing $\text{NH}_3(\text{g})/\text{NH}_4^+(\text{p})$ predictions
193 with measured ammonia gas-particle partitioning. We also evaluate the impact of neglecting
194 gaseous ammonia from the calculation applying the model even with just aerosol-phase data as
195 already done in previous studies⁶.

196

197 3.2. Estimating gaseous ammonia in fogs

198 Although fogs scavenge most of the aerosol and a large fraction of the water-soluble gases of
 199 interest for pH determination (namely NH_3 and HNO_3), a portion remains in the gas phase in quasi-
 200 equilibrium with the fog water. If the atmospheric concentration of gaseous ammonia in fog
 201 ($\text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}$) is known, it can be included in the thermodynamic analysis. To determine $\text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}$, we
 202 first assume that NH_3 is in equilibrium with fog water NH_4^+ , and then correct to account for any
 203 apparent departure from this equilibrium because we use the bulk fog water pH³¹. Following Guo
 204 et al.²⁶, the fraction of available NH_3 that partitions to the fog water at equilibrium, $\varepsilon_{\text{NH}_4}$, is given
 205 by:

$$206 \quad \varepsilon_{\text{NH}_4} = \frac{H_{\text{NH}_3}^* RT \text{LWC}_f}{1 + H_{\text{NH}_3}^* RT \text{LWC}_f} \quad (3)$$

207 where T is the measured temperature in K, LWC_f is the measured liquid water content of the air in
 208 g m^{-3} , R is the ideal-gas constant equal to $0.082 \text{ atm L mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$, and $H_{\text{NH}_3}^*$ is the effective Henry's
 209 law constant calculated at the measured fog water pH:

$$210 \quad H_{\text{NH}_3}^* = H_{\text{NH}_3} \frac{K_{a_1}}{K_w} [\text{H}^+] \quad (4)$$

211 where H_{NH_3} is the Henry law constant for NH_3 equal to 62 M atm^{-1} at 298 K, $K_{a_1} = 1.7 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$
 212 and $[\text{H}^+]$ is the hydronium ion concentration in the fog water.

213 Given that the fog water pH, and concentration of ammonium and liquid water are known,
 214 equations (3) and (4) can be combined to give $\text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}^{\text{eq}}$:

$$215 \quad \text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}^{\text{eq}} = \frac{\text{NH}_4^+(\text{fog})}{H_{\text{NH}_3} \frac{K_{a_1}}{K_w} RT [\text{H}^+] \text{LWC}_f} \quad (5)$$

216 where $NH_{3(fog)}^{eq}$ is the equilibrium concentration of ammonia in the fog, and $NH_{4(fog)}^+$ is the fog
217 water ammonium concentration.

218 Ricci et al.³², investigating the uptake of soluble gases by fog droplets, showed that deviations
219 from bulk equilibrium can occur – thus should be accounted for, at least approximately. For this,
220 we define an equilibrium deviation ratio, $D_r = NH_{3(fog)}/NH_{3^{eq}(fog)}$, as the ratio between estimated
221 ($NH_{3(fog)}$) and bulk equilibrium gas-phase ammonia concentration. If D_r is constrained from
222 observations, it can then be used together with Equation 5 to provide the estimated concentration
223 of ammonia in the fog:

$$224 \quad NH_{3(fog)} = \left[\frac{D_r K_w}{H_{NH_3} K_{a1} RT} \right] \frac{NH_{4(fog)}^+}{[H^+] LWC_f} \quad (6)$$

225 Given that our analysis refers to the bulk composition of fog-water (in which we cannot keep
226 track of size and pH of the single droplets), actually the deviation ratio (D_r) can change depending
227 on the duration and characteristics of the fog-event (as already hypothesized and empirically
228 measured by Pandis and Seinfeld³¹ and by Ricci et al.³²) and especially depending on the pH of
229 the fogwater solution. Pandis and Seinfeld³¹ proved that for all fogs the difference in pH among
230 droplets of different sizes (larger droplets tend to be more alkaline as they form on alkaline dust
231 particles), even if the system is in equilibrium, leads to a supersaturation of the bulk aqueous phase
232 compared to the gas phase. In order to account for this effect too, using the available measured
233 data (referring to the last 2 years analyzed, 2017-18), we estimate (following the steps described
234 in the Supplementary Section S1) the possible range of D_r values due to different fog-events
235 (Figure S1) and we explicitly determine the relationship between D_r and the measured fog-pH for
236 the 25-years dataset (Figure S2).

237 We tested consequently different D_r in the range suggested by our analysis as well as the
238 uncorrected estimation (i.e., $D_r=1$) corresponding to the equilibrium (Supplementary Section S1).
239 In particular, we compare the performance of the different D_r estimations in term of the agreement
240 between (a) simulated and observed ammonia/ammonium concentrations at SPC and (b) estimated
241 $\text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}$ concentrations and $\text{NH}_{3(\text{g})}$ measurements available also in other places of the Po Valley,
242 like Lombardy (where $\text{NH}_{3(\text{g})}$ is measured since 2003).
243 The results of this comparison suggests that D_r expressed as function of fog pH is more
244 appropriate, as it corresponds and correlates well with the available parallel $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and $\text{NH}_{3(\text{g})}$
245 measurements at SPC (Figure S3) and leads to estimated $\text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}$ concentrations which are
246 comparable with other Po Valley background sites (Figure S4).

247

248 **4. Results and Discussion**

249 *4.1. Model evaluation*

250 The ability of the thermodynamic analysis of fog water composition to estimate aerosol pH is
251 tested first for a subset of data collected from August 2017 to October 2018 focusing on ammonia
252 partitioning. In this period measurements of both fog and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ compositions are available as well
253 as $\text{NH}_{3(\text{g})}$ concentrations. ISORROPIA-II was used to simulate the partitioning in the system using
254 the fog composition and the estimated $\text{NH}_4^+(\text{fog}) + \text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}$ as inputs for the total ammonia. These
255 predictions are then compared against the measurements of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ NH_4^+ and $\text{NH}_{3(\text{g})}$ concentrations.

256 The predictions of ISORROPIA-II for the ammonia/ammonium concentrations obtained
257 from the fog water composition and estimated NH_3 inside the fog are quite consistent with those
258 using as inputs the measured $\text{NH}_{3(\text{g})}$ and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ aerosol composition (Figure 1). The differences in
259 concentrations are on average $-1\pm 3\%$ for gas-phase ammonia and $8\pm 3\%$ for particulate ammonium

260 (Figure S2). The two approaches also result in consistent pH values with an average difference of
261 0.06 ± 0.27 pH units (Figure 2).

262 Moreover, a direct comparison of the fog water and $PM_{2.5}$ composition for all the parallel
263 available samples (63 samples spanning from 2011 up to 2018) is also reported in Table S1 and
264 Figure S6 showing a general agreement. This confirms that the fog water thermodynamic analysis
265 provides a consistent alternative for predicting the pH in the ambient aerosol with reasonable
266 accuracy.

267 If we do not include the observed gas-phase NH_3 , the predicted pH decreases by 1.01 ± 0.12
268 units using $PM_{2.5}$ composition (Figure 2). This difference (hereinafter defined as ΔpH_{AerPM}) is
269 consistent with findings of previous studies^{6,8,33} that neglect consideration of gas-phase NH_3 when
270 inferring aerosol pH. The difference of the fog water-based pH predictions ($AerFOG$ pH) with and
271 without the estimated gas-phase ammonia (ΔpH_{AerFOG}) is slightly higher at 1.09 ± 0.34
272 respectively (Figure 2). The calculation of the ammonia concentration from the fog water
273 composition is unambiguous and leads to considerably improved pH estimates.

274

275 *4.2. Aerosol pH trend in the last 25 years*

276 The aerosol pH was estimated using the proposed approach based on the 577 fog water
277 samples collected at SPC over the last 25 years. In order to investigate typical conditions, the daily
278 mean values of RH and T (calculated as average of the 24h of each corresponding day) were used
279 for the ISORROPIA-II calculations, considering them as the best approximation of the average
280 conditions that particles were exposed to before the onset of fog.

281 The time trend of estimated aerosol pH over the last 25 years is showed in Figure 3. We used
282 annual averages to help ensure that errors are independent and identically distributed, as suggested

283 by Hess et al.³⁴. The variability of the aerosol pH during each year is considerable. In 1997, for
284 instance, the calculated pH ranged from 1.38 to 5.51. The variability among years is also
285 remarkable with the highest annual average of 5.18 in 1993 and the lowest of 3.66 in 2010. Given
286 this high variability, the general trend of the aerosol pH over time is identified by applying an
287 interquartile-range rule to remove the extreme values from the annual averages (see
288 Supplementary Section S3), and we obtain a net pH decreasing trend for the whole period 1993-
289 2018 at a 99% confidence interval (Figure 3 and Figures S7-S8). The calculated means from
290 applying the interquartile-range rule show that during 1993-2002, average aerosol pH was 4.62
291 (with the highest annual average of 5.18 in 1993) while from 2003-2012 it was 4.53 (with the
292 highest value of 5.10 in 2004) dropping to an average value of 4.27 over the 6 years between 2013
293 and 2018 (with a maximum value of 4.31 in 2016).

294 Given the importance of the gas-phase ammonia concentration inside the fog layer,
295 $\text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}$, in the determination of the aerosol pH trend over time, an additional evaluation of the pH
296 variability due to different possible estimations of the gaseous ammonia concentrations is in the
297 Supplement (sections S4 and S5, Figure S9-S11). All tests confirm the decreasing trend of the
298 aerosol pH based on the fog composition (AerFOG pH) within a limited range of variability
299 depending on the chosen gaseous ammonia estimation. Aerosol acidity has increased by
300 approximately 0.5-1 pH units over the examined 25-year period.

301 The fog water pH is also shown in Figure 3 and it shows an increasing trend at a 99%
302 confidence interval (using least squares regression). Giulianelli et al.¹⁶ already analyzed this
303 increasing trend of fog pH at SPC and related it to the decreasing concentrations of the major acidic
304 species NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} (Figure S12). SO_2 and NO_x emissions have been reduced in Italy but also
305 throughout Europe – without a concurrent decrease in fog water content during episodes. This

306 behavior is consistent with other European and American datasets (Pye et al.² and references
307 therein).

308 These different trends, although counterintuitive at first glance, are consistent with the
309 thermodynamics of the fog and aerosol systems. The water concentration in the fog is not driven
310 by the amount of aerosol, but rather only by the meteorological conditions – especially the cooling
311 rate when fog is forming. In contrast, aerosol liquid water scales with the amount of aerosol. As a
312 result, aerosol pH tends to change much less with aerosol amount (because liquid water changes
313 accordingly)^{1,10}. At the same time, there is the potential for a small decrease in pH with reduced
314 aerosol, because relatively larger amounts of ammonium need to volatilize to establish equilibrium
315 between the gas and particulate phases¹. As this ammonium leaves the particles, the main cation
316 that neutralizes the acids is depleted. This means that aerosol pH tends to become more acidic even
317 if the strong acidic components (sulfate and nitrate formed from SO₂ and NO_x) are reduced.
318 Another factor that can reduce aerosol pH is the change of meteorological parameters (RH and T)
319 observed at SPC along the 25-years period (Figure S13). The role of the different drivers of the
320 observed trends will be discussed in a subsequent section.

321

322 *4.3 RH and T variability effect on pH predictions*

323 In our analysis, as already mentioned, we considered daily mean values of relative humidity
324 and temperature as the best approximation of the conditions that particles were exposed to before
325 the onset of fog. To understand how predicted aerosol pH varies throughout each day depending
326 on the RH and T, we repeat the simulation using the RH and T continuously measured during the
327 fog-events and averaged over the fog-sampling time periods, which possibly represent the
328 atmospheric conditions most close to the fog-scavenging.

329 The resulting pH also shows a decreasing annual average trend (Figure S14), with a
330 reduction of ~ 1.5 pH units over the 25-year period. The difference between the two trends is
331 indicative of the effect of the diurnal variability in meteorology on the predicted aerosol pH.
332 Taking these differences into account, we can state that the aerosol pH has declined by 0.5-1.5
333 units over the last 25 years.

334 The different slope of the two pH trends in Figure S14 indicates the important role of RH
335 in determining aerosol pH by influencing the aerosol liquid water content. To further investigate
336 this effect, we used a constant RH value equal to 99, 95, 90, 85, 80, 75, and 70% and repeated the
337 pH calculation. The aerosol pH values calculated using RH=99% are systematically higher than
338 all the others (Figure S15). For lower values of the RH the trend becomes weaker, highlighting the
339 importance of RH in pH determination at least in a region such Po Valley characterized by high
340 RH.

341

342 *4.4. Drivers of aerosol pH reduction*

343 To understand the drivers of the observed aerosol pH reduction, we apply a multiple linear
344 regression analysis on the simulated aerosol pH, following the approach of Rosenfeld et al.³⁵. A
345 first regression is applied to the aerosol pH with all the independent variables (ions composition
346 and meteorological parameters) used by ISORROPIA-II in order to calculate the total R^2 . The
347 regression is then repeated, sequentially omitting a variable at a time to retrieve the contribution
348 of each individual variable to the total variance explained (or R^2). The strongest contribution is by
349 the total ammonium (NH_4^{TOT} , i.e., gas plus particle-phase), representing alone 35% of the total
350 variance explained, followed by sulfate (SO_4^{2-}) and RH contributing 17 and 16% each respectively,
351 and calcium (Ca^{2+}) contributing 11% (Table S2). Grouping the variables by category we find that

352 the major ions (NH_4^{TOT} , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} and Cl^-) are responsible for 61% of the variability, the
353 meteorological parameters (RH and T) for another 23%, and the non-volatile cations (K^+ , Na^+ ,
354 Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+}) for the remaining 16%.

355 These findings confirm the importance of the aerosol chemical composition changes along
356 the years, but point out the important contribution of decreasing RH and increasing T already
357 observed at SPC (Figure S13) in determining the pH trend. This influence should be accounted for
358 when considering future climate change and its interaction with air quality.

359

360 *4.5. Relationship between wintertime/fog-related pH and other seasons*

361 Our analysis shows a decreasing trend in aerosol pH based on the fog water chemical
362 composition. However, the fog composition is representative only of the period between
363 November and March when fog events actually occur, and in particular only of the days in which
364 fog occurs. Nevertheless, based on the pH sensitivity to RH (Figure S15) and on the difference
365 between the average RH during foggy days and during all winter (Table S3) we can expect a
366 change in pH estimation of about 0.2-0.3 units due to the variability of RH in wintertime (which
367 never drops below 80% on a seasonal average basis). Regarding seasons without fog events, the 7
368 years (2011-2018) of available aerosol data²⁴, allow a robust characterization of the SPC aerosol
369 pH seasonality over the recent past. A strong seasonality of aerosol pH (calculated using monthly
370 average of the available gaseous ammonia measurements for constraining the model, as described
371 in Supplementary Section S9, Figure S16) is recognizable, with the highest average values of 4.19
372 during winter (in good agreement with the pH calculated from fog-composition in the same period
373 2011-2018) and the lowest of 2.61 during summer (Figure S17). The variation of more than 1.5
374 pH units between winter and summer can be the result of the seasonal changes in meteorological

375 conditions (mean wintertime temperature and RH are 276 K and 85% while the summertime ones
376 are 297 K and 62%, respectively) but also of the changing emissions like biomass burning in the
377 wintertime, agricultural activities and photochemical processes during summer³⁶. These seasonal
378 ranges are consistent with the seasonality reported in other locations (e.g., Pye et al.², and
379 references therein).

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383 **5. Implications**

384 Information on aerosol pH trends over time is limited in Europe as well as around the
385 world, owing to the scarcity of relevant data. Long-term monitoring programs for cloud/fog
386 composition and acidity are also limited, but there are locations around the world where such
387 measurements have been made routinely, or at least periodically, over periods of a decade or more.
388 Our analysis suggests a novel way to calculate pre-fog aerosol pH using fog compositional data in
389 a thermodynamically consistent way, which can be useful to evaluate long-term trend of particles
390 acidity also in other region of the world for which data are available (e.g., Central Valley in CA;
391 Whiteface mountain, NY; etc.²).

392 The Po Valley dataset used in this work shows an increasing trend of fog water pH¹⁶. We
393 show for the first time that this increasing pH of cloud/fog water may not be indicative of the trend
394 in aerosol acidity. In the case of the Po Valley the fog and the aerosol have opposite trends during
395 the last 25-years. We demonstrate that this aerosol pH reduction trend is thermodynamically robust
396 and it is driven by the contemporary decrease of the corresponding air pollutants due to the
397 environmental policies and by the changing meteorological parameters (RH and T), possibly a

398 result of regional climate change. The Po Valley is dominated by ammonia emissions and its
399 aerosol is characterized by pH and liquid water content levels similar to those in E. Asia during
400 haze episodes²⁶.

401 The Po Valley is a well-known air quality hotspot characterized by particulate matter (PM)
402 levels well above the limit set by the European Air Quality Directive and by the World Health
403 Organization. These high concentrations are dominated during the cold season (almost half of the
404 year) by ammonium nitrate (which during winter represents 26-43% of total PM_{2.5} mass²⁰). Given
405 their semi-volatility and their acid-base activity, nitrate and ammonium are the aerosol species
406 most sensitive to pH. Nenes et al.³⁷ developed a new conceptual framework explicitly considering
407 pH, aerosol liquid water content and temperature as the main parameters controlling secondary
408 inorganic PM sensitivity. Figure 4 places the Po Valley aerosol pH (both based on fog and aerosol
409 data) in this framework. Based on this the SPC area from November to March (fog season) is in
410 the regime in which aerosol nitrate formation is highly efficient. This is true for the aerosol pH
411 calculated both by fog water (i.e., referring to foggy days) and by PM_{2.5} composition (i.e., including
412 both foggy and non-foggy wintertime days of 2017-18).

413 Considering the definitions of Nenes et al.³⁷ and the average values of temperature and aerosol
414 liquid water content corresponding to the PM_{2.5} samples collected at SPC during the cold season
415 (280 K and 28.8 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, respectively), we calculate the threshold for the change of acidity regime
416 to be at a pH of ~ 0.5 . This pH value is well below the lowest observed pH values (3.76 as annual
417 average for 2010). However, if the decreasing trend of aerosol pH continues in the future and the
418 pH drops to the threshold level, aerosol nitrate will remain almost exclusively in the gas phase as
419 HNO₃, regardless of the amount present. If and when this change will happen depends on the rate
420 of future reduction in emissions of NH₃ and NO_x (precursors of aerosol ammonium and nitrate)

421 and on the changes of T and RH. Increasing T and decreasing RH will tend to shift the threshold
422 to higher pH values as the effect of the liquid water content decreases. For the time being, the
423 winter-time composition has been gradually moving along the years from the top right
424 (HNO_3/NH_3 -sensitive regimes) toward top left side of the graph (HNO_3 sensitive regime) (Figure
425 4), mostly because the aerosol liquid water content in particular has decreased significantly due to
426 changes in PM concentrations and also to decreasing RH (Figure S13). pH has seen less of a drop
427 because of these changes.

428 Currently, the PM sensitivity regime remains in the HNO_3 -sensitive area throughout the
429 year, with a tendency however to be close to the NH_3 sensitive regime during summer (Figure 5).
430 This seasonality of the PM sensitivity in Po Valley is important for effective pollution control
431 policies. This means that currently, NO_x controls would be most effective for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ reduction in
432 the Po valley both during summer and winter. In the future however, seasonal transitions to the
433 NH_3 -sensitive region may occur, meaning that NH_3 reduction policy may become increasingly
434 necessary. Future work will focus on the implications of the emission and meteorological trends
435 for the deposition of reactive nitrogen³⁸.

436

437 **ASSOCIATED CONTENT**

438 **Supporting Information.** The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS
439 Publications website. Deeper descriptions of the modeling methods (e.g., estimation of gaseous
440 ammonia from fog-water composition, NH_3 estimation effect on aerosol pH variability and RH
441 sensitivity test); statistical analysis of the pH trend; details on the trends of pollutants and

442 meteorological parameters; details on the results of the multiple linear regression analysis to
443 study the drivers of aerosol pH reduction. (PDF)

444

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449 **Notes**

450 The authors declare no competing financial interest.

451

452 **Author Contributions**

453 MP, and AN developed the acidity inference method and designed the research; SD, LT, SF, and
454 MCF managed the fog-sampling campaigns; MP, SD, SG, MR, and FM contributed to the
455 chemical analyses; DB, and AT performed aerosol sampling and ammonia measurements; MP,
456 AN, SP, and SD wrote the paper; SP, MR, SF, MCF, SG, and SD contributed the scientific
457 discussion and paper correction. All authors have given approval to the final version of the
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464

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614

615 **Figure 1.** Evaluation of the ISORROPIA-II ammonia/ammonium concentrations: simulated
 616 concentrations of ammonia (panel a) and ammonium (panel b) are plotted in y-axes against the
 617 corresponding observed/estimated values (x-axes). Red markers refer to the measured $\text{NH}_3(\text{g})$ and
 618 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ aerosol composition; green markers represent the partitioning obtained from the fog-water
 619 composition and estimated NH_3 inside the fog. Dashed line shown is the 1 : 1 for comparison.

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623 **Figure 2.** pH calculated by ISORROPIA-II from PM2.5 composition (AerPM2.5 pH) and from
 624 fog-water composition (AerFOG pH). Panel a: time series of AerPM2.5 (dashed lines) and
 625 AerFOG pH (markers) for the evaluation dataset. Panel b: AerPM2.5 (y-axis) and AerFOG (x-
 626 axis) pH values for parallel samples. The dashed lines indicate delta pH = 1, 0, and -1. In both the
 627 panels, black line and markers represent the calculation made without gaseous ammonia ($\text{NH}_{3(g)}$)
 628 as input, while red line and markers represent the result using particle/fog $\text{NH}_4^+(p)$ + gaseous
 629 ammonia measured ($\text{NH}_{3(g)}$) or estimated by fog composition ($\text{NH}_{3(fog)}$), respectively.

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631
 632 **Figure 3.** Fog and aerosol pH trends as measured directly into fog-water or calculated by
 633 ISORROPIA-II. Black circles are the annual average of the pH measured; red squares are the
 634 annual average values of aerosol pH calculated by ISORROPIA-II starting from the fog ionic
 635 composition with the gaseous estimated $\text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}$ as input (pH AerFOG+ $\text{NH}_{3(\text{fog})}$). Green triangles
 636 are the annual average values of aerosol pH calculated by ISORROPIA-II starting from PM2.5
 637 ionic composition with the measured gaseous NH_3 as input (pH AerPM2.5+ $\text{NH}_{3(\text{g})}$). Error bars
 638 represent the standard deviations of the measured/calculated pH values.

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641
 642 **Figure 4.** Distribution of aerosol pH versus aerosol liquid water content from both fog-
 643 composition (blue points) and PM_{2.5} composition (brown points) inside the chemical domains of
 644 aerosol sensitivity to NH₃ and NO_x emissions as introduced by Nenes et al. (2020). The blue line
 645 defines the characteristic pH when aerosol is sensitive to changes in available nitrate and the red
 646 line in ammonia. These are calculated for the average temperature of the winter-periods (280 K).
 647 PM_{2.5} data are for 2017-2018 wintertime samples for which both NH₄⁺_(p) and NH_{3(g)} measurements
 648 are available. Bigger markers indicate the average values of the corresponding multi-year period
 649 reported below each of them: white symbols refer to calculations based on the fog water data and
 650 the orange circle the aerosol and gas-phase ammonia data.

652

653 **Figure 5.** Seasonality of the distribution of aerosol pH versus Liquid Water Content inside the
 654 chemical domains of aerosol sensitivity introduced by Nenes et al. 2020. Characteristic pH for
 655 defining when aerosol is sensitive to changes in available nitrate (blue lines) and ammonia (red
 656 lines) are calculated for the annual average temperature (=287 K, solid lines) \pm its standard
 657 deviation (=295 K, dotted lines, and =278 K, dashed lines, respectively).